

REVIEW ARTICLE

On Review of the Cluster Point of a Set in a Topological Space

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Received: 01-07-2019; Revised: 10-09-2019; Accepted: 18-10-2019

ABSTRACT

If X be a topological space and A subspace of X , then a point $x \in X$ is said to be a cluster point of A if every open ball centered at x contains at least one point of A different from x . In the preliminary sections, review of the interior of the set X was discussed before the major work of section three was implemented.

Key words: Set, subset, closure and interior of set, topological space, cluster point of a set

INTRODUCTION

The word “set” in this context is used to denote the collection of well-defined object, for example, a set of books or set of student and so on. Here, let our set be denoted by the capital A and the numbers of the set by any small letters of the alphabet. Hence, the $x \in A$, we say A is a subset of B if every element of $A \subset B$ while $A \subseteq B$ is used for proper subsets.

$$A \cup B = \{x : x \in A \text{ or } x \in B\} \text{ while } A \cap B = \{x \in A \text{ and } x \in B\}.$$

Definition 1.1

A subset A of a topological space X is said to be closed if the set $X-A$ is open, for example, the subset $[a, b]$ of R is closed because it is complement $R - [a, b] = (-\infty, a) \cup (b, +\infty)$ is open.^[1]

Theorem 1.1

Let X be a topological space. Then, the following conditions hold:

1. \emptyset and X are closed

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2. Arbitrary intersections of closed sets are closed
3. Finite unions of closed sets are closed.^[2]

Theorem 1.2

Let Y be a subspace of X . Then, a set A is closed in Y if and only if it equals the intersection of a closed set of X with Y .^[3]

Theorem 1.3

Let Y be a subspace of X . If A is closed in Y and Y is closed in X , then A is closed in X . Proof to above three equations is in James Monks p. 94-95.^[4]

CLOSURE AND INTERIOR OF A SET

Given a subset A of a topological space X , the interior of A is defined as the union of all open sets contained in A and the closure of A is defined as the intersection of all closed sets containing A .

The interior of A is denoted by $\text{Int } A$ and the closure of A is denoted by $\text{CL } A$ or by \bar{A} ; obviously, $\text{Int } A$ is an open set and \bar{A} is a X closed set. Therefore, $\text{Int } A \subset A \subset \bar{A}$

If A is open, $A = \text{Int } A$ while if A is closed $A = \bar{A}$

Theorem 2.1

Let Y be a subspace of X and let A be a subset of Y . The closure of A in Y equals $\bar{A} \cap Y$.^[5]

Theorem 2.2

Let A be a subset of the topological space X .

- a) Then, $x \in \bar{A}$ if and only if every open set U is containing x intersects A .
- b) Supposing the topology of X is given by a basis theory $x \in \bar{A}$ if and only if every basis element B containing x intersects A .^[6,7]

Proof

Consider the statement (a), it is a statement of the form $P \Leftrightarrow Q$. Let us transform each implication to its contrapositive, thereby obtaining the logically equivalent statement $(\text{not } P) \Leftrightarrow (\text{not } Q)$. Written out it is the following:

$x \notin \bar{A} \Delta$ there exists an open set U containing x that does not intersect A .

In this form, our theory is easy to prove. If x is not in \bar{A} , the set $U = x - \bar{A}$ is an open set containing x that does not intersect A as desired. Conversely, if there exist an open set U containing x that does not intersect A , then $X - U$ is a closed set. By definition of the must contain \bar{A} , the set $X - U$ must contain A ; therefore, x cannot be in \bar{A} . Statement (b) follows readily. If every open set containing x intersects A so does every basis element B containing x , because B is an open set.

Conversely, if every basis element containing x intersects A so does every open set U containing x because U contains a basis element that contains x . Hence, U is an open set containing x , i.e. U is a neighborhood of x .

Therefore, if A is a subset of the topological space X , then $x \in \bar{A}$ if and only if every neighborhood of x intersects A .

CLUSTER POINT (LIMITED POINT OR ACCUMULATION POINT) OF THE SET A

This is another way of defining the closure of a set.

Definition 3.1

Let X be a topological space and A be a subspace of X . A point $x \in X$ (not necessary in A) is said to be a cluster point or a limit point or an accumulation point of A if every open ball centered at x contains

at least one point of A different from x (i.e., x is a limit point of A if $B_r(x) - \{x\} \cap A \neq \emptyset$ for real number $(r > 0)$.^[3]

Equivalent definition

If A is a subset of a topological space X and if x is a point of X , we say that x is a limit point (or cluster point or accumulation point of A if every neighborhood of x intersects A in some point other than x itself. Alternatively, x is a limit point of A if it belongs to the closure of $A - \{x\}$.

Another alternative definition

When $X = \mathbb{R}$ and $A \subseteq X = \mathbb{R}$, we say that x is a limit point of R if $\forall \delta > 0, (x - \delta, x + \delta) \Delta A - \{x\} \neq \emptyset$

Definition 3.2

The set of all limit point of A denoted by A' is called the derived set of A .^[7]

Definition 3.3

A subset of A of a metric space X is said to be closed if it contains all its limit points.^[4]

Theorem 3.1

Let A be a subset of the topological space X and let A' be the point of A , the $\bar{A} = A \cup A'$

Proof

If x is in A' , every neighborhood of x intersects A (in a point different from x). Therefore, $x \in \bar{A}$. Hence, $A' \subset \bar{A}$. Since by definition $A \subset \bar{A}$, it follows that $A \cup A' \subset \bar{A}$ to demonstrate the reverse inclusion we let x be a point of \bar{A} and show that $x \in A \cup A'$ supposed that x does not lie in A . Since, $x \in \bar{A}$, we know that every neighborhood U of x intersects A in a point different from x . Then, $x \in A'$ so that $x \in A \cup A'$, as desired.

Theorem 3.2

Let $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}$.

- I. If x has a neighborhood which only contains finitely many members of A , then x cannot be a limit point of A .

II. If x is a limit point of A , then any neighborhood of x contains infinitely many members of A .^[2]

Proof I

Let U be a neighborhood of x which contains only a finite number of point A that is $U \cap A$ is finite. Suppose $U \cap A \setminus \{x\} = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\}$. We show that there exists $\delta > 0$ such that $(x - \delta, x + \delta) \cap U$ does not contain any member of $A \setminus \{x\}$. Since both $x - \delta, x + \delta$ and U neighborhood of x so is their intersection.

This will prove that there is a neighborhood of x containing no element of $A \setminus \{x\}$ hence proving x is not a limit point of A . Let $\delta = \min \{|x - y_1|, |x - y_2|, \dots, |x - y_n|\}$ since x is not equal to $y_i, \delta > 0$. Then, $(x - \delta, x + \delta)$ contains no point of A other than x , thus proving our claim. Proof of II follows immediately from I.

Corollary 3.3

No finite set can have a limit point.

Proof

Follows immediately from Theorem 2.2.

Theorem 3.4

Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}$, then

- i. $A \cup L(A) = \bar{A} = A \cup A'$
 - ii. $L(A) \cup L(B) = L(A \cup B)$, i.e., $A' \cup B' = (A \cup B)'$
 - iii. $L(A)$ is closed, i.e. A' is closed.
 - iv. If U is open, then $L(U) = U$, i.e., $U' = U$
- (i) above was clearly captured in the proof of Theorem 2.1 while (ii) and (iv) are follow ups of already proved theorems above.

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